

Recommended citation: Mendonça, J., Pinto, C. M. A., & Nicola, S. (2019). Effectiveness of active-learning methodologies in Math Courses for Engineering Students. In Nagyn, B. V., Murphy, M., Järvinen, H.-M., & Kálmán, A. (Eds.), *Varietas delectat... Complexity is the new normality. SEFI 47th Annual Conference* (pp. 755-769). European Society for Engineering Education (SEFI), Budapest, Hungary. DOI: 10.5281/zenodo.14656539.

Effectiveness of Active-learning Methodologies in Math Courses for Engineering Students

Effectiveness of AL in Math Courses for Engineering Students

J. Mendonça, C.M.A. Pinto², S. Nicola
School of Engineering, Polytechnic of Porto
Porto, Portugal

Centre for Mathematics, University of Porto²
Porto, Portugal

Conference Key Areas: Diversity in Engineering Education; Fundamentals of engineering education: mathematics and physics

Keywords: active-learning methods, jigsaw, eduScrum, effectiveness

ABSTRACT

Global changes in Education are a consequence of changing demography, increasing globalisation, emerging demands on sustainability and the rapid evolution of digital era. These issues develop a generation Z of students, which are more independent than their Millennial counterparts. They prepare for their future, have college expectations and use educational technology for their academic progress. This causes a disruption and presents new challenges and opportunities for educators and administrators. Gen Zers, the demographic cohort after the Millennials, expect knowledge to be delivered to them in different ways. They are open to learn in environments where they are active players, where they do research, discuss results, multitask, and decide themselves. Professors have to fully take advantage of these Gen Zers' potential and think of new ways of introducing course materials, both in and beyond the classroom. This will exploit their ability to think critically, be problem solvers, and train their resilience to be prepared for society challenges. Thus, how can teachers involve students more actively in class? Active-learning (AL) methods are part of the answer. In an AL framework, students are directly involved in their learning process, instead of merely listen.

The purpose of this article is to summarize the implementation of AL methods (Jigsaw, eduScrum, Think-Pair-Share) in Math courses at the School of Engineering of the Polytechnic of Porto. Students' perceptions of the application of AL in class are discussed. We hope to contribute to fruitful discussions of what should be best practices of application of AL methods in Math courses for Engineers.

1 INTRODUCTION

Generation Z is disrupting the way learning takes place. Gen Zers strive to be directly and actively involved in acquiring knowledge. They refuse to passively listen to what

the teachers have to tell them. They want to attend classes in a fully engaged way. They don't want to go to classes to merely take notes to memorize, and write them down in an exam later on. Gen Zers tend to be more hands-on, more problem-solvers, they like interactive classes, and social learning environments, over traditional teaching methods. They are used and feel comfortable in studying collaboratively with other students, taking advantage of digital tools, like online forums, chats, amongst others. Moreover, as children of the digital era, the students of today want knowledge to take place at any time and so courses' contents are expected to be available on-demand, easily accessed, and not be limited to the classroom environment. These students are also more career-focused and are themselves driving changes in college curriculum, whenever this possibility is at hand. Thus, Gen Zers are mastering the change in the way they learn. They are pointing to a more learner-centered framework where students are owners of their own futures [1].

Providing our students with more stimulating learning environments and new approaches to teaching is part of a broader Education Strategy. Students are inspired mostly when they feel engaged, and this requires active-learning (AL) methods, to break with the passive way of delivering classes. Moreover, teachers are also requested to adequate teaching options to individuals and groups, as well as addressing students' individual needs [2].

Active-learning techniques promote creativity, cognitive processing, critical thinking, resilience, collaborative work, discussion [3,4].

AL has been steadily taking its own place in the world of Education. Australia was one of the first countries to embrace it, in 1990. New Zealand and the United Kingdom were the next countries in this sequel [5]. Researchers have been focusing on teaching in distinct environments and in new ways [6], as well as in exploring AL impact in improvement of learning outcomes [7]. More recently, in 2018, Holmes focused on the amount of energy, time and resources each student spends, in virtual learning environments, to promote their own knowledge [8].

There are several ways of encouraging AL environments, namely Jigsaw, eduScrum, Think-Pair-Share, Problem-Based Learning, Flipped classroom, to name a few. Jigsaw is an AL strategy in which students work in small groups and are directly engaged with the working material. Students learn the topics by themselves and explain them to their peers. This promotes an increased knowledge and understanding of the topics and go against the typical exam-driven learning [9]. EduScrum is an adjustment of the Scrum Project management technique to Education [10]. In companies, Scrum is a technique favoring teamwork between collaborators in a productive and enjoyable way. With eduScrum, students organize and manage their own learning process. The teacher is only a guide, determining why and what to study. This type of collaborative educative process boots student's creativity, mutual collaboration, constant improvement, professional communication, teamwork, and critical thinking [11].

Think-Pair-Share (TPS) is a simple learning tool in which students find the solution to a given proposed problem. This strategy promotes students' oral communication skills, team work, and discussion, since they have to think individually about the problem, and then share their ideas on how to solve it with their peers. This discussion boosts students' participation and engagement in class and deepens the understanding of the reading materials [12].

With the aforementioned ideas in mind, the paper is organized as follows. In Section 2 we review several cases of application of AL methods to teach Math Courses in Bachelor degrees at the School of Engineering of the Polytechnic of Porto, since the

academic year of 2017/2018. In Section 3, we discuss results of statistical analyses of students' perceptions of the implementation of these AL techniques in their courses. In Section 4 we conclude this work.

2 CASE-STUDIES OF AL AT ISEP

In this section we will present and describe the pedagogical methodologies and evaluation methods applied to a three case studies at ISEP, on the academic year of 2017/2018, first and second semester. The three case studies were at the courses Linear Algebra and Analytical Geometry (ALGAN) and Computational Mathematics (MATCP) at the Bachelor Informatics Engineering Degree, and in Calculus (CALCL1) at the Bachelor Biomedical Engineering Degree.

2.1 A case study at Linear Algebra and Analytical Geometry.

The first case study where it was implemented the active learning methodologies was on the academic year of 2017/2018, first semester in the course of Linear Algebra and Analytical Geometry of the Bachelor Informatics Engineering Degree at ISEP. This study target 308 students, separated in 5 theoretical lessons (T) with about 60 students each and 10 practical classes (TP) with more or less 35 students each. 'Typical' (traditional) T classes sizes can run from 70 to 100 students, with varying levels of individuals' needs and support, whereas TP classes consist at most of 30 students.

Theoretical Lessons

In the T classes, we implemented a hybrid teaching framework: some classes are taught using the traditional approach (TM), and some are taught applying the Jigsaw method of AL methodology. The Jigsaw framework is based on a self-teaching strategy and was applied in 3 T classes. The students of the other 3 T classes were taught by the traditional method (TM), with the usual talk and chalk approach. Implementing Jigsaw in a class is achieved through the following procedure. The teacher must prepare notes for each of the topics, and these notes are made available to all students a priori. In class, the teacher starts by giving information about the global topic and the 4 subtopics which are intended to be learned. Students are then gathered in groups of 4, the so called Home groups. Each student studies one particular subtopic individually. This task may take 10 minutes. Then, all students who have learned subtopic i , $i = 1, 2, \dots, 4$, move to an Expert group, for that specific subtopic i . There, they take 10 minutes to discuss between peers the key points of that subtopic and how they will teach it to the other members of their Home groups, when they return. After returning, they have 10 minutes to teach their peers. In the end of this activity, the teacher verifies the degree of understanding of the 4 subtopics by all students.

Practical Lessons

In order to implement the active learning approach with different methods, we applied in the practical classes of the Linear Algebra and Analytical Geometry course, the eduScrum methodology, as a part of an AL process. The 10 practical lessons were also divided in two categories, in 5 of them the eduScrum method was implemented and in the other 5 was used the traditional method. The course consists of 12 weeks. Each practical class of 37 students was split in 6 or 7 groups, of 5 or 6 students each. Every two weeks, students have Sprints, where they have to do a set of proposed exercises and are evaluated accordingly. In this scenario students are exposed to some discussion between their peers and with the teacher, which is an essential part of a mathematical classroom. Students in class are asked to form groups of 4/5 members each (the team). After forming the groups, students chose a Student Master, who is responsible for distributing the tasks to each member of the group. This procedure ends with a Sprint Review, where the sprint assessment is performed. The latter consists of 3 components: 1) assessment of tasks performed - usually calculating the weighted average of accepted tasks; 2) activities not accepted have a 0; 3) assessing students' individual contribution by analysing the team's Scrum board. In the Sprint retrospective students discuss key points of the solved tasks and make a brief report of what went well, what went wrong, what should be improved in the next Sprint.

Figure 1 shows the distribution of each pedagogical method allocated to each form. In three theoretical lessons (T1, T4 and T5) is applied a self-teaching method, based in the Jigsaw framework. In the other two lessons (T2 and T3) we maintain the traditional teaching method (TD). Concerning practical lessons, these are divided in two categories: a) in 5 forms is implemented the eduScrum methodology; b) in the others 5 forms the traditional method is used.

Fig. 1. Distribution of each pedagogical method allocated to each class in ALGAN [11]

The Fig.2 presents the excel worksheet for evaluating the students in the course of ALGAN. For 12 weeks the students had 5 Sprints, where each of them weight 25%, 20%, 15%, 20%, 20% respectively. Then the students had two written assignment, with individual assessment each one weight 40% each. The total of Sprints value 20% and the individual assessment 80%.

2.2 A case study at Computational Mathematics.

The second case study in 2017/2018 where it was implemented the active learning methodologies was in the academic year of 2017/2018, second semester in the course of Computational Mathematics of the Bachelor Informatics Engineering Degree at ISEP. This study targeted 384 students, separated in 5 theoretical lessons (T) with about 80 students each, 11 practical classes (TP) and 21 Practical Labs (PL) of 15 students each. ‘Typical’ (traditional) T classes sizes can run from 80 to 100 students, with varying levels of individuals’ needs and support, whereas TP classes consist at most of 30 students and PL runs from 15 to 22 students. Figure 2, shows the distributions of different pedagogical methods (JigSaw, eduScrum and traditional way of teaching) applied to each class. The course has a team composed by 9 professors with more than 20 years of experience at ISEP.

Fig. 3. Distribution of each pedagogical method allocated to each class in MATCP

It was created a table, table 1, where each teacher knew the type of lectures, methodology applied, tasks and evaluation for each class.

Table. 1. Distribution of each pedagogical method allocated to each class.

Teacher	Lectures	Methodology	Task	Evaluation
X	T/Practical	Traditional	Blackboard exercises	"-----"
	Practical Labs	Traditional	Blackboard exercises	Moodle feedback/Excel sheet
Y	Theoretical	Jigsaw	Coach	"-----"
		Traditional	Teaching	"-----"
	Practical Labs	Traditional	Blackboard exercises	Moodle feedback
		Eduscrum	Coach	Eduscrum/Excel sheet
Z	T/Practical	Eduscrum	Coach	Eduscrum/Excel sheet
	Practical Labs	Traditional	Blackboard exercises	Moodle feedback
		Eduscrum	Coach	Eduscrum/Excel sheet
W	Theoretical	Jigsaw	Coach	"-----"
		Traditional	Teaching	"-----"
	Practical Labs	Traditional	Blackboard exercises	Moodle feedback
		Eduscrum	Coach	Eduscrum/Excel sheet
K	T/Practical	Eduscrum	Coach	Eduscrum/Excel sheet
		Traditional	Blackboard exercises	"-----"
	Practical Labs	Traditional	Blackboard exercises	Moodle feedback
		Eduscrum	Coach	Eduscrum/Excel sheet
Q	Theoretical	Traditional	Teaching	"-----"
	T/Practical	Traditional	Blackboard exercises	"-----"
	Practical Labs	Eduscrum	Coach	Eduscrum/Excel sheet
P	T/Practical	Traditional	Blackboard exercises	"-----"
	Practical Labs	Traditional	Blackboard exercises	Moodle feedback
M	Practical Labs	Traditional	Blackboard exercises	Moodle feedback
		Eduscrum	Coach	Eduscrum/Excel sheet
A	T/Practical	Eduscrum	Coach	Eduscrum/Excel sheet
	Practical Labs	Traditional	Blackboard exercises	Moodle feedback
		Eduscrum	Coach	Eduscrum/Excel sheet

Theoretical Lessons

The theoretical lessons followed the same strategy of ALGAN classes. In the T classes, some classes were taught using the traditional approach (TM), and some were taught applying the JigSaw method of AL methodology.

Practical Lessons

To implement the active learning approach with different methods, we applied in the practical classes of the Computational Mathematics course, the eduScrum methodology, as a part of an AL process. The 11 practical lessons were also divided in two categories, in 5 of them the eduScrum method was implemented and in the other 6 was used the traditional method. The course consists of 12 weeks. Each practical class of 37 students was split in 6 or 7 groups, of 5 or 6 students each. Every two weeks, students had Sprints, where they have to do a set of proposed exercises and are evaluated accordingly (please see table1). In this scenario students are exposed to some discussion between their peers and with the teacher, which is an essential part of a mathematical classroom.

Practical Lab Lessons

Practical Lab Lessons were also divided in two models, 13 using the traditional method and 6 of them the eduScrum method. Each PL of from 15 to 22 students were split in 4 to 5 groups, of 4 students each. Every two weeks, students had Sprints, where they had to do a set of proposed exercises and were evaluated accordingly (please see table1). PL where prevails the traditional method, the exercises were done in the blackboard by the teachers and the evaluation of the different topics of the subject were done every two weeks (called sprints). These sprints were done by each student in the Moodle platform in the form of quizzes. The PL classes that prevails the eduScrum method, the role of the teacher was coaching the students. The teacher ask the right questions, to promote greater self-awareness and foster more informed decision making, so that the students can learn something. In this type of lessons is not the role of teachers that will solve problems, but rather, promote discussions, observations, pre-observations to collaboratively promotes the students learning. This will help students to think critically and be a life long learner. Every two weeks, Sprints, they had to present to the teacher the tasks solved and teachers put the evaluation of each student in an excel sheet, Figure 4.

Number	Name	Class	Team/Work	Week 2			Week 3			Week 4			Week 5		
				26/02/2018	to	05/03/2018	to	10/03/2018	to	17/03/2018	to	19/03/2018	to	24/03/2018	
				PL1	Proposed	PL2	Proposed	PL3	Proposed	PL4	Proposed				
				Presences	Total of Exerc Done	Presences	Total of Exerc Done	Mark	Presences	Total of Exerc Done	Mark	Presences	Total of Exerc Done	Mark	

Fig. 4. Excel Sheet for evaluate students sprints in MATCP

2.3 A case study at Integral Calculus.

The third case study, where it was implemented the active learning methodologies, was on the academic year of 2017/2018, first semester in the course of Integral Calculus (CALCL1) of the Bachelor Biomedical Engineering Degree at ISEP. This study targeted 79 students with theoretical lessons (T) and 2 practical classes (TP) with more or less 35 students each. In the theoretical classes was applied the Jigsaw technique to deliver the theoretical concepts of the course. With this pedagogical technique students learned in both base groups and expert groups. They actively engage in the learning process and have a better understanding of their learning. The eduScrum methodology defines that incorrect work is not acceptable. In the sprints of the practical classes, students will work in groups. The groups will have to Peer-review to improve the quality of the work (Peer Feedback pattern). This work tool aims to provide students with information about the evolution of their learning process. In the practical lessons we apply the eduScrum technique in solving problems associated with the contents of the lectures. The students learn in groups. There will be time for questions of students, where they can place and be answered questions regarding the curricular unit.

For 16 weeks the students had 5 Sprints with 30% as total. Then the students had two written assignment, with individual assessment each one value 35% each.

3 ANALYSIS OF STUDENTS' PERCEPTIONS

Students' perceptions of the implementation of AL techniques along the previous referred courses were evaluated from their responses to posed questionnaires. Students' opinions were rated according to the scale 1-Strongly disagree, 2- Disagree, 3-Slightly agree, 4-Moderately agree, 5-Strongly agree. We started in Calculus (50 responses) and ALGAN (209 responses) courses, in first semester of academic year 2017/18. These courses were followed by the MATCP (102 responses) course in the second semester of the academic year 2017/18. The first questionnaire has been updated due to inner characteristics of the different courses, but the main purpose, which was to measure students' perceptions to the AL framework remained unchanged.

The implementation of these methodologies in general has promoted a positive impact in students due to the teamwork approach, and evaluation based on their self-effort. In Fig.4, are shown the results (*mean ± standard deviation*) of students' perceptions on several issues concerning AL, obtained for the three courses. The scale in the x-axis is [1,6], since there are cases of values of the standard-deviation greater than one. As we observe in Fig. 4, CALCL1 is a small dimension course, with a smaller number of students, presenting very positive and with small variability responses. The ALGAN course revealed positive means with higher variability for the same questions.

The questionnaires' of MATCP suffered an upgrade in the questions posed to the students, since this course contains different class typologies and requires Excel programming tasks. Moreover, the authors with the experience from the 1st semester notice that the questionnaire should have different questions to gauge and assess more precisely the implementation of new methodologies applied in each course.

The questions on Table 2, "Work in assigned groups to complete homework and other projects" ($p=0,002$); "Be graded based on the performance of my group" ($p=0,000$); "Solve problems in a group during class" ($p=0,000$), "Do hands-on group activities during class" ($p=0,001$), present significant differences between the courses. The students in CALCL1 course show higher mean values than ALGAN courses.

In MATCP the authors notice that students have good perceptions on these methodologies, evidenced by the following questions "Discuss concepts with classmates during class"; "Solve problems in a group during class"; "the discussion of the topics between peers"; "I consider myself resilient when facing difficulties in some exercises in laboratorial classes" with mean values over 3.5.

Fig. 4. Mean±standard deviation of Students' perceptions on CALCL1, ALGAN and MATCP Courses.

Table. 2. Mann-Whitney Test -ALGAN vs CALCULUS

	Mann-Whitney U	p-value
Work in assigned groups to complete homework and other projects	3801	0.002
Discuss concepts with classmates during class	4374	0.057
Be graded based on the performance of my group	3056.5	0.000
Solve problems in a group during class	3439	0.000
Do hands-on group activities during class	3771	0.001
Do you consider Jigsaw a useful learning tool?	4650.5	0.206
Did you feel more motivated to learn with the Jigsaw methodology?	5006.5	0.633
In your opinion, can the eduscrum methodology help you to develop soft skills for your future professional life?	5068.5	0.728
Do you agree with the learning by doing method in the practical classes?	4775	0.325

4 EFFECTIVENESS OF THE TWO TEACHING APPROACHES

We present here the analysis of the grades in the course of Computational Mathematics (MATCP). We compared the two groups TM – traditional method versus EDS- Eduscrum method, concerning, Test 1 grades, Test 2 grades, Final grades without Sprints’ grades, and Final grades with Sprints. We considered for this study the students who’ve done all assessments along the course. We observe significant differences between these two groups for all cases as shown by the mean difference t-test results (Table 3).

Table. 3. Descriptive statistics and t-test for the two teaching approaches, TM and EDS.

		Test1 Grades	Test2 Grades	Final Grades without Sprints Grades	Final Grades with Sprints Grades
N	TM	151	151	151	151
	EDS	101	101	101	101
Mean	TM	11.235	8.551	9.893	10.868
	EDS	12.688	9.771	11.230	12.287
Standard deviation	TM	3.776	3.588	3.177	2.990
	EDS	3.577	3.407	3.022	2.655
t-stat		-3.055	-2.701	-3.337	-3.869
p-value		0.001	0.000	0.000	0.000

Moreover, from the observation of the mean grades we can conclude that the EDS method seems to produce better outcomes than the TM approach. The standard deviations are greater in the TM method, though not statistically significant by the F-test (variances). These results are in accordance with the ones already available in the literature, concerning assessment of students' of active-learning classes [13].

5 CONCLUSIONS

In this paper, we reviewed case-studies of application of AL techniques in Math courses at ISEP, since the first semester of the academic year of 2017/2018. We implemented stimulating learning environments and new approaches to teaching in different class typologies, namely eduScrum, Jig-Saw. We analysed statistically data from questionnaires given to students of the different courses. Students' perceptions were positive with respect to the application of AL techniques in these courses. Students enjoy working in groups and the increase in the responsibility of their learning process. We have also done a comparative statistical analysis of the students' grades along the semester in the written assessments for one Math course. The results reveal significant differences between the two groups of students, for all cases, as shown by the mean difference t-test results. The EDS approach produces better results, the mean grades are better for EDS students. Altogether, the results from the soft skills questionnaire and from the grades, reflect the boost of cognitive and social students' skills, reported in the literature for students engaging in active-learning frameworks. We highlight student's creativity, mutual collaboration, constant improvement, professional communication, teamwork, and critical thinking.

These novel methodologies have been developed in the scope of an Erasmus+ project, DrIVE-MATH - Development of Innovative Mathematical Teaching Strategies in European Engineering Degrees, which has had its beginning in September 2017, and will end in August 2020 <https://ec.europa.eu/programmes/erasmus-plus/projects/eplus-project-details/#project/b1a82053-e093-4526-90d6-aa1efe1c6a1b>

ACKNOWLEDGMENTS

CMUP's author was partially supported by CMUP (UID/MAT/00144/2013), which is funded by FCT (Portugal) with national (MEC) and European structural funds (FEDER), under the partnership agreement PT2020. All authors wish to thank Erasmus+.

Co-funded by the
Erasmus+ Programme
of the European Union

REFERENCES

- [1] Forbes <https://www.forbes.com/sites/sievakozinsky/2017/07/24/how-generation-z-is-shaping-the-change-in-education/#17e1e6236520> Last accessed April 8 2019.
- [2] BECKER A., CUMMINS S., DAVIS M., FREEMAN A., GIESINGER C. and ANANTHANARAYANAN V. (2017) NMC Horizon Report: 2017 Higher Education. Edition. Austin, Texas: The New Media Consortium.
- [3] BONWELL C.C., EISON A.J. (1991) Active Learning: Creating Excitement in the Classroom in ASHEERIC Higher Education. Report No. 1. Washington, DC: George Washington University Press.
- [4] EISON J. (2010) Using active learning instructional strategies to create excitement and enhance learning, 2010. <http://www.cte.cornell.edu/documents/presentations/Eisen-Handout.pdf> Accessed April 8, 2019.
- [5] NEGREA S. (2018) World of active learning in higher ed <https://www.universitybusiness.com/article/world-active-learning-higher-ed>. Accessed April 8, 2019.
- [6] EDUCAUSE (2018) <https://www.educause.edu/>. Accessed April 8 2019.
- [7] THE INNOVATIVE LEARNING ENVIRONMENTS AND TEACHER CHANGE (ILETC) (2018) <http://www.iletc.com.au/>. Accessed April 8, 2019.
- [8] HOLMES N. (2018) Engaging with assessment: Increasing student engagement through continuous assessment. Active Learning in Higher Education, Vol. 19, No. 1, pp. 23-34.
- [9] MENDONÇA J., PINTO C.M. AND NICOLA S. (2018) ACTIVE-LEARNING: SELF-MOTIVATION IN MATH COURSES, INTED2018 - 12th International Technology, Education and Development Conference, Valencia, Spain, DOI: 10.21125/inted.2018.0332.
- [10] SCRUM METHODOLOGY (2018) <https://www.inloox.com/company/blog/articles/the-scrummethodology/>. Accessed April 8, 2019.
- [11] NICOLA S., PINTO C.M. and MENDONÇA, J. (2018) The role of education on the acquisition of 21st century soft skills by Engineering students. Changing Higher Education One Teacher at a Time, Editors: Gabriel, B., Campos, G.A., Oliveira, J.D., Nascimento, M.M., Valente, R., Neto, V., Universidade de Aveiro, Aveiro, 1-4.
- [12] Think-Pair-Share. <http://www.adlit.org/strategies/23277/>. Accessed at April 8 2019.

-
- [13] DUVALL S., HUTCHINGS D.R., and DUVALL R.C. (2018) Scrumage: A Method for Incorporating Multiple, Simultaneous Pedagogical Styles in the Classroom. SIGCSE 2018: 928-933.